

Caregiving: Do females fare better than males

1* Dr.Neeta Sinha 2* Dr.Sakshi Pindoria 3*Dr.Supriya Pal

Abstract

India is a collectivist country. Here elderly/ ill are responsibility of the family members, not the society. When a disabled is cared for by the family members he is likely to feel better and happier. This brings positivity and happiness among the mentally challenged. Owing to the social construct, women, especially in India, are preferred as the natural caregivers for persons with mental illness. Patients with mental illness need assistance or supervision in almost all of their daily chores which often places a major burden on their caregivers, thereby placing the latter at a great risk. However in many cases men too play a prominent role as caregiver. The present study was undertaken to find out whether caregiving was easier for male or female caregivers of patients with different psychological and psychiatric disorders. Though caregiving is challenging for either, it gives immense satisfaction and joy to the family members, which is reflected in their positive approach. The total sample size of the study was 228 (86 male and 142 female). The data was collected from Bhuj and in and around Ahmedabad with the help of Involvement Evaluation Questionnaire (IEQ). Despite having significant variance between life challenges, males appeared to have a better quality of life compared to women.

Key words: Caregiver, mental health, patient, disorder illness, positive approach.

1* Dr.Neeta Sinha 2* Dr.Sakshi Pindoria 3*Dr.Supriya Pal

1* Associate Professor, School of Liberal Studies, Pandit Deendayal Energy University, Gandhinagar

2* Counsellor

3* Assistant Professor, School of Liberal Studies, Pandit Deendayal Energy University, Gandhinagar

Introduction

Since care offered by carers is concerning and arduous, it may, sooner or later, change their lives in terms of physical, economical, psychological, and social aspects. Reduced efficiency may be experienced at home and at workstation thus losing wages; this, in addition to the health care costs of the patients, may affect the caregivers financially, leading to or worsening insufficiency. However India is a family oriented collectivistic country and family members are the primary care givers in majority of the cases. Carers, along with the patients, are prone to experience social costs encompassing disrupted social networks, stigma and discrimination, in turn exposing the former to high levels of depression, stress and anxiety. However the satisfaction they tend to feel in caring for their loved ones is unparalleled. These changes in terms of social, economic and psychological aspects may critically affect the carers' quality of life. Quality of life is an individual's awareness of their situation in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live along with their goals, expectations, standards and concerns. The quality of life of carers is vital in understanding the quality of care that is provided to people with mental illness to aid recovery or stability which in turn affects the progress and result of such people and if done with love and care brings positivity in the lives of the patients. Though caregivers are fundamental in giving care to patients with severe mental illness and they do face hardships but in the Indian context the family members would not let anybody else take care of their babies.

A growing trend has been observed in India where women are shifting from the traditional position of homemakers to the working class, seeking financial autonomy and security. In the study by Associated Chambers of Commerce and Industry (2014), working women (21–52 years of age) were surveyed; 68% of the women were afflicted with lifestyle ailments like obesity, depression, chronic backache, diabetes, and hypertension.

According to WHO (1997), those needing primary health care in developing countries make up for around 20%; of the total population. These people are stricken with often associated disorders of anxiety and depression, symptoms of which may not always be recognised.

Treating mental health disorders is of paramount concern. According to WHO (2017), in India alone the burden of mental health problems is 2,443 DALYs (Disability Adjusted Life Year) per 100,000 population, and the age-adjusted suicide rate per 100,000 population is 21.1.

Between 2012-2030 it is projected that the economic loss due to mental health conditions in India will be 1.03 trillions dollars.

Mental illness and caregiving

Health, as defined by WHO (2018), is not only the non-appearance of disease or weakness but a condition encompassing somatic, psychological and social prosperity. An individual who dons the responsibility of a dependent patient in order to provide for the physical and psychological needs is known as a caregiver. Assistance or supervision in almost all the day to day activities of a psychiatric patient usually places a heavy load on their carers, making them prone to various mental and physical health problems. Physical, emotional and financial toll of providing care is termed as 'caregiver burden'. With the progression in illness, there is a tremendous liability on the caregiving person. Caregiving of persons with mental illness is challenging as sometimes it is demanding and at other times, it may be fulfilling to caregivers. No one will work harder for the health and well-being than family.

In India, family members are the caregivers for persons with mental illness as there are extremely limited alternative facilities and family members are preferred for caring. The changing social milieu in India such as urbanization and nuclear family is placing significant burden on family members. However the carers from the family try to remain positive and provide the best to the mentally ill family members under all circumstances.

Caregiver's profile in Indian context

Unpaid care delivered by family members or friends for persons with chronic illnesses or functional impairment is known as family caregiving. Even with increasing number of males assuming the role of caregiving world over, women are still considered as the chief providers of informal care for members with mental illnesses. Worldwide, caregivers of the elderly with dementia are usually their wives or daughters. The caregivers, themselves, are usually middle-aged with a substantial share of them being elderly. Caregivers of schizophrenia or mood disorders patients are generally their parents, commonly mothers, and they too are often aged. It can be assumed that caregivers of people with mental illnesses in India follow a similar profile. However, this assumption can seldom be backed up by reliable data. The majority of studies on caregivers of patients with schizophrenia and mood disorders are hospital-based.

The biased samples of these studies are not expected to be representative of the entire population of caregivers. Nevertheless, a few community studies on the subject (e.g. Janardhana et al.) do show that women predominate as caregivers, but the number of male caregivers is increasing. Most caregivers are middle-aged or elderly and are commonly parents of patients. Most caregivers in India are older women caring for their husbands or younger women caring for their parents. Consequently, caregivers are more often middle-aged than elderly.

In the Indian society, caregiving is generally done by the family collectively, especially by parents or the spouse. If married, the burden habitually falls on the spouse, and if the spouse is a woman, she is looked up on as a natural carer. Owing to religious and cultural beliefs, one is morally held responsible to execute the said role. If we look at our shastra's therein also "Sewa" is considered to be paramount. The ved, puran and The Gita talk about positivity through 'sewa' bhav. They emphasize on the role of Positive Psychology and happiness through being a part of the social system wherein we gain happiness and well-being through positive participation in the lives of our loved ones.

Method

Sample: The total population being 228 consists of 147 female sample and 81 male sample.

Fig. Gender of Respondents

Interpretation: The above chart relating to the gender of respondents depicts that 62% of respondents are females and rest 38% are males.

Instrument: Involvement Evaluation Questionnaire (IEQ) is a self-report 33 items tool consisting of (1) tension subscale (2) supervision subscale (3) worrying subscale and (4) urging subscale, and the last 4 items forming a ‘generic’ sub-scale, as witnessed in the last four weeks. Responses are rated on a 5-point Likert scale, ‘never’, ‘sometimes’, ‘regularly’, ‘often’, and ‘always’, and scored as 0, 1, 2, 3 and 4. The Cronbach’s alpha value, when computed for the present study, comes out to be 0.863 which says that the set of items are closely related and there is a high degree of internal consistency in the data collection tool used.

Results & discussion

To assess the differences in quality of life of caregivers over gender Mann Whitney test was used.

Based on tension

H0: There is no significant difference between the quality of life of males and females.

Ha: There is significant difference between the quality of life of males and females.

Table: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Tension	228	1.198343	.9411482	.0000	4.0000
Gender	228	1.36	.480	1	2

Table: Ranks

	Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Tension	Females	147	101.53	14924.50
	Males	81	138.04	11181.50
	Total	228		

Here, the mean value of females signifies they have lower mean rank and for males the value of mean rank is higher. The higher mean signifies that males ranked higher on tension scale. They are more tensed than females.

The total population being 228 consists of 147 female sample and 81 male sample. The mean rank for females is 101.53 and that for males is 138.04 indicative of the fact that more than females it's their counterparts who face tension while taking care of a patient with a psychiatric or mental illness. Females, in their day to day life have to make many adjustments which may be a resultant that they are less tensed while caring. Also in the Indian context the females are brought up in such a manner that care and nurturing is a part of their upbringing. They look at it as a role they are supposed to perform and do it without much difficulty. They are able to take care of the family members and also stay in a positive frame of mind. They may face challenges but that does not deter them from performing their duties.

Table: Test Statistics

	Tension
Mann-Whitney U	4046.500
Wilcoxon W	14924.500
Z	-4.006
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

Significant at 0.05 level
Grouping variable: gender

Here, the p value is 0.000 which is less than the level of significance which is 0.05. This says that null hypothesis is rejected and so alternate hypothesis says that there is significant difference between the two groups. Mean rank of females is statistically significantly lower than the males. This means the tension scale varies over gender and males and females experience different tension levels. Males are more tensed than females.

In the Indian scenario it is generally the females who are expected to look after the task of caregiving as since childhood they are trained to adapt to living with changing needs of those

around them; while men are made to focus on the monetary earning aspect. Hence when a man is expected to carry out the task of caregiving it not only becomes taxing but also makes him feel helpless due to tension.

Based on supervision

H0: There is no significant difference between the quality of life of males and females.

Ha: There is significant difference between the quality of life of males and females.

Table: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Supervision	228	.917398	1.0175284	.0000	3.6667
Gender	228	1.36	.480	1	2

Table: Ranks

	Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Supervision	Females	147	101.62	14937.50
	Males	81	137.88	11168.50
	Total	228		

Here, the mean value of females signifies that they have lower mean rank and for males the value of mean rank is higher. The higher mean signifies that males ranked higher on supervision scale. They do more supervision than females.

Males, as they generally deal with the outside world more, have a pattern of comparatively being more meticulous than their counterparts especially when it comes to supervising an individual; so accordingly when they are anticipated to take on the character of a carer they prove to be more vigilant. Females are careful but they aren't as watchful as men as they are loaded with other household chores.

Table: Test Statistics

	Supervision
Mann-Whitney U	4059.500
Wilcoxon W	14937.500
Z	-4.048
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.000

Significant at 0.05 level
Grouping variable: gender

Here, the p value is 0.000 which is less than the level of significance which is 0.05. This says that null hypothesis is rejected and so alternate hypothesis says that there is significant difference between the two groups. Mean rank of females is statistically significantly lower than the males. This means the supervision scale varies over gender and males and females experience different supervision levels. Males need more supervision than females

This implies that the supervision carried out on the patients of mental illness by males and females differ. Females in India are nurturers since childhood hence they are able to manage quite a few things on their own. Whereas Men need more of supervision and guidance to be able to be effective care givers. However they too approach care giving with a positive approach and are able to do caregiving fairly well.

Based on worrying

H0: There is no significant difference between the quality of life of males and females

Ha: There is significant difference between the quality of life of males and females.

Table: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Worrying	228	2.068713	1.1274207	.0000	4.0000
Gender	228	1.36	.480	1	2

Table: Ranks

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Females	147	104.57	15372.00
Worrying Males	81	132.52	10734.00
Total	228		

Here, the mean value of males signifies that they have higher mean rank and for females the value of mean rank is lower. The higher mean signifies that males ranked higher on worrying scale. They are more worried as caregivers for their patients than females.

In our society it is presumed that as a woman who does mainly home chores hardly has anything to worry about; which in the present context is a reality. Women are so used to nurturing since childhood that caregiving does not have a major burden on them. She has to cater to the needs of each and every one present in the house and at times and she is able to do that with a lot of ease. However sine the male are not so used to caregiving and nurturing they find it difficult to get take all the extra burden and tend to remain worried.

Table: Test Statistics

	Worrying
Mann-Whitney U	4494.000
Wilcoxon W	15372.000
Z	-3.069
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.002

Significant at 0.05 level
Grouping variable: gender

Here, the p value is 0.002 which is less than the level of significance which is 0.05. This says that null hypothesis is rejected and so alternate hypothesis says that there is significant difference between the two groups. Mean rank of females is statistically significantly higher than the males. This means the worrying scale varies over gender and males and females

JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT & ENTREPRENEURSHIP

ISSN: 2229-5348

UGC Care Group 1 Journal

experience different worrying levels. Males are more worried than females.

Based on urging

H0: There is no significant difference between the quality of life of males and females

Ha: There is significant difference between the quality of life of males and females.

Table: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
urging	228	1.92434	1.083977	.000	4.000
Gender	228	1.36	.480	1	2

Table: Ranks

	Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
urging	Females	147	108.90	16009.00
	Males	81	124.65	10097.00
	Total	228		

Here, the mean value signifies that females have lower mean rank and for males the value of mean rank is higher. The higher mean signifies that males ranked higher on urging scale.

They do more urging than females.

While caring naturally comes to females, men need to make an extra effort in accumulating the skill. This may be a result of why men urge more while caring for a patient than females.

Table: Test Statistics

	Urging
Mann-Whitney U	5131.000
Wilcoxon W	16009.000
Z	-1.727
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.084

Significant at 0.05 level
Grouping variable: gender

Here, the p value is 0.084 which is more than the level of significance which is 0.05. This says that null hypothesis is accepted which says that there is no significant difference between the two groups. Mean rank of females is statistically significantly lower than the males. This means the urging scale varies over gender and males and females experience different urging levels. Males urge more than females. They tend to do several follow-ups and keep doing that till they are able to get the entire work done.

Based on other areas

H0: There is no significant difference between the quality of life of males and females.

Ha: There is significant difference between the quality of life of males and females.

Table: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Items not Included	228	2.0077	.83902	.00	4.00
Gender	228	1.36	.480	1	2

Table: Ranks

	Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Items not included	Females	147	122.52	18010.00
	Males	81	99.95	8096.00
	Total	228		

Here, the mean value of females signifies they have higher mean rank and for males the value of mean rank is lower. The higher mean signifies that females ranked higher on the quality of life.

Table: Test Statistics

	Items not included
Mann-Whitney U	4775.000
Wilcoxon W	8096.000
Z	-2.494
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.013

Significant at 0.05 level
Grouping variable: gender

Here, the p value is 0.013 which is less than the level of significance which is 0.05. This says that null hypothesis is rejected and so alternate hypothesis says that there is significant difference between the two groups. Mean rank of females is statistically significantly higher than the males. This means that on females are different have a better quality of life. This could be attributed to the fact that females are comfortable in care giving and they do not find it a burden. They can manage the caregiving processes along with their other chores very smoothly and lead a relatively hassle free life. This positivity towards life's challenges makes them function smoothly and lead a good quality of life.

Summary

Gender plays a noteworthy role in caregiving. In the present study it was found that the female caregivers outnumbered male carers. Females, who worry more, on an average have a lower quality of life, which signifies that despite having significant variance between life challenges, males appeared to have a better quality of life compared to women. Males as primary care givers are lesser in number, whilst they too experience tension, males appear to be more supervised and urge their patients more. Even on the all other items scales, significant difference was observed between the two. We can therefore conclude that positivity towards life is required in order to experience a better quality of life. Mostly over a period of time both males and females tend to accept the fact and caregiving being a part of their daily routine comes to them naturally

Even in a study by Rammohan et al. (2002), similar result was observed that greater burden was experienced by female caregivers than males, especially when it came to family relationships, occupational burden, and caregiver's health. But despite that females learn to lead a life of dignity and hope.

A profound interaction with the carer based on the gender variable helped in articulating that females, who form a majority, require strong social and familial support in terms of emotional support and finance in order to lead a happy and positive life.

References

1. Ampalam, P., Gunturu, S., and Padma, V. (2012). "A comparative study of caregiver burden in psychiatric illness and chronic medical illness." *Indian Journal of Psychiatry, Medknow*, 54(3), 239–243.
2. Banerjee and Bidisha (2015) "Impact of Culture in Caregiving Experiences in the Context of Mental Illness: A Brief Review" *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology, Questia*, 41(2), 272.
3. Bohra, N., Srivastava, S. and Bhatia, M.S. (2015) "Depression in women in Indian context." *Indian Journal of Psychiatry, Medknow*, 57(6), 239-245.
4. Chakrabarti, S. (2016) "Research on family caregiving for mental illness in India and its impact on clinical practice: Are we doing enough to help families?" *Indian Journal of Social Psychiatry, Medknow*, 32(1), 19-24.

5. Chaturvedi, S.K., Basavarajappa, C. and Ahamed, A. (2015) "Mental Health Care Bill, 2013 and United Nations Convention on the rights of persons with disability: Do they go hand in hand?" *Indian Journal of Social Psychiatry*, Medknow, 31(2), 107-111.
6. Dare, A., Hardy, J., Burgess, P., Coombs, T., Williamson, M. and Pirkis, J. (2008) *Carer Outcome Measurement in Mental Health Services: Scoping the Field*. Retrieved from Google Scholar, https://www.amhocn.org/sites/default/files/publication_files/carer_outcome_measurement_final_report_20080924.pdf
7. Iyer, M. (2017) "7.5% Indians suffer from mental disorders: WHO report." Retrieved from The Times of India http://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/articleshow/57344807.cms?utm_source=contentofinterest&utm_medium=text&utm_campaign=cppst
8. Murthy, R.S. (2016) "Caregiving and caregivers: Challenges and opportunities in India." *Indian Journal of Social Psychiatry*, Medknow, 32(1), 10-18.
9. Ramos-Cerqueira, A.T., Rodrigues, A.T., Torresan, R.C., Negreiros, A.P. and Vitorino, C.N. (2008) *Emotional burden and psychological morbidity in caregivers of patients with obsessive-compulsive disorder*. Retrieved from ResearchGate https://www.researchgate.net/publication/247242839_Emotional_burden_and_psychological_morbidity_in_caregivers_of_patients_with_obsessive-compulsive_disorder/citations
10. Sharma, L (2017) "A Descriptive Co-relational study on Burden, Social Support and Family Wellbeing among Caregivers of Mentally Ill Patients in Mansik Aarogayashala, Gwalior (M.P.)." *Asian Journal of Nursing Education and Research*, A & V Publications, 7(2), 228-230.
11. Srivastava, S. (2005). "Perception of burden by caregivers of patients with schizophrenia." *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*, Medknow, 47(3), 148-152.
12. ZamZam, R., Midin, M., Hooi, L.S., Yi, E.J., Ahmad, S.N., Azman, S.F., ... Radzi, R.S. (2011) "Schizophrenia in Malaysian families: A study on factors associated with quality of life of primary family caregivers." *International Journal of Mental Health Systems*, BioMed Central, 5(1), 16.